

Absent Links: LLMs, Search Infrastructures, and the Information Ecosystem

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1. Introduction

Search engines are central to today's knowledge infrastructure: they provide the illusion of instant, unmediated, impartial access to "the world's information" (Google, n.d.). Recently, there has been a shift in the paradigm of online search, away from algorithms that structure the display of links to websites towards the integration of large language models (LLMs) that provide direct answers to search queries. Based on a view of knowledge as situated and embodied, I critically examine this trend by pointing out the position of search algorithms in the broader environment of the information ecosystem of online search.

2. Situated and Sealed Knowledges

The theoretical understanding of 'knowledge' of this contribution is based on Donna Haraway's conception of the term, which she introduced in her 1988 seminal essay "*Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective*" (Haraway, 1988). Haraway argues that all knowledge is inherently partial and intimately tied to the embodied position of its knower. With that, she challenges the traditional notion of what she terms a "view from above, from nowhere, from simplicity"—a detached, universal objectivity (Haraway, 1988, p. 589). Rather than dismissing the concept of objectivity altogether, Haraway proposes a feminist objectivity that is rooted in situated perspectives and that acknowledges the importance of context, power, and positionality.

This embodied, situated view of knowledge shows that proposals to integrate LLMs into online search engines are based on a disembodied understanding of knowledge as they hide the inherent situatedness of knowledge and information (Lindemann, 2024). By introducing the concept "*Sealed Knowledges*" in reference to Haraway (1988) and Mühlhoff (2018), I previously showed that the introduction of LLMs to online search engines "seals off" certain knowledges, making them difficult to find (Lindemann, 2024). When integrated into search engines, LLMs produce singular, plausible-sounding answers to search queries, obscuring the complex knowledge space of possible query answers. This is important not the least because LLMs integrated into search engines are part of the broader (online) *Information Ecosystem*.

3. LLMs and the Information Ecosystem

Although the metaphor of an "information ecosystem" is well-established, it is rarely applied to examine the specific impacts of integrating LLMs into online search. In this contribution, I argue that doing so is crucial. The information ecosystem is intrinsically relational and its various components are deeply interdependent. These elements, which I term 'systems of relations', are relational themselves

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and can be both material and non-material. The 'systems of relations' include not the least corporations and capital, material infrastructures, technological and software infrastructures, information, knowledge (as understood in the aforementioned, situated sense), data, socio-technical narratives and meaning making processes.

Therefore, when conceptualizing the consequences of integrating LLMs into online search, it is essential to consider their effects on all the different systems of relations within this ecosystem. The integration of LLMs into online search has various consequences, ranging from the loss of serendipity in searches (Shah and Bender, 2022) and the easy spread of (political) misinformation (AlgorithmWatch and AI Forensics, October 5th, 2023), to environmental impacts due to the required material infrastructures (see Luccioni and Strubell, 2024) and societal understanding of knowledge (Lindemann, 2024), as well as to reduced training in information literacy (Shah and Bender, 2022) and reduced critical thinking (Lee et al., 2025). In order to understand the full impact of LLMs being integrated into online searches, it is thus important to consider this in the context of the information ecosystem.

4. Conclusion

In this contribution I argue that a relational view of online search as situated within the information ecosystem is crucial to understanding the impact and consequences of integrating LLMs into online search. While the focus of critical inquiry into online search is often on misinformation (which is undoubtedly important), LLMs have further reaching consequences that are only seen through a relational, networked perspective.

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